

INDUCED ANISOTROPY IN POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

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Outline

- The principles of Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) and how can we use them
- Morphological effects of Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) on nanocomposites
- Induced anisotropy in PLA/nanocarbons 3D printed composites:
 - Mechanical – for bio-mimicry
 - Electrical – for “materials as devices”

The principals of Fused Filament Fabrication

3D printing of thermoplastic composites

The principals of Fused Filament Fabrication

- Materials Parameters:
 - Printing temperature (affected by polymer T_m)
 - Build plate temperature (affected by polymer T_g)
- Product Quality Parameters:
 - Printing speed (faster vs. more precise)
 - Layer thickness (better resolution vs. faster printing, voids)
 - Air gaps (faster & more precise vs. voids)
- Printing Progress Parameters:
 - Building orientation
 - Raster angle
 - Infill percentage
 - Infill pattern

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The effect of FFF on nanocomposites

- Product Quality Parameters:
 - Layer Thickness

The effect of FFF on nanocomposites

It's not a bug

Induced anisotropy for bio-mimicry

*Scorpio
Maurus
Palmatus*
Class: Arachnids
Phylum: Arthropods

Induced anisotropy for bio-mimicry

Induced anisotropy for bio-mimicry

The need for 3D printable conductive polymers

S. Dul et al. *Polymers* **2020**, 12, 101; doi:10.3390/polym12010101

P.F. Flowers et al. / *Additive Manufacturing* 18 (2017) 156–163

S.W. Kwok et al. / *Applied Materials Today* 9 (2017) 167–175

The system

The filler	Carbon Black (CB)	Graphene (Gn)
Wt. %	27%	12.7%
Aspect ratio	1.60 ± 0.61	$23.73 \pm 13.91 \leq$
Visual		

Karutzero Y. et al. *in preparation*

The system

Karutzero Y. et al. *in preparation*

The system

- 3 different line directions:
 0° , 45° , 90° .
- 2 different layer heights:
 $100\mu\text{m}$, $250\mu\text{m}$

Anisotropy dependence on nanoparticle morphology

The Conductance as Function of the Printing Angle for 250 μ m Layer Thickness (1 mA)

Anisotropy dependence on Printing Parameters

Karutzero Y. et al. *in preparation*

Iby and Aladar Fleischman
Faculty of Engineering
Tel Aviv University

הפקולטה להנדסה
ע"ש איבי ומלדר פליישימן
אוניברסיטת תל-אביב

Surface conductivity affected by printing parameters

PLA/CB

PLA/Gn

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Volumetric conductivity affected by printing parameters

Morphologic explanation to electrical anisotropy

PLA_CB_250_0	PLA_CB_100_45	PLA_CB_250_90	PLA_CB_100_0
-0.93±9.54°	-44.59.39±11.23°	-90.39±6.27°	2.63±12.51°
+1.02%	-0.91%	+0.43%	+2.90%

Morphologic explanation to electrical anisotropy

PLA_Gn_100_0	PLA_Gn_250_45	PLA_Gn_100_90	PLA_Gn_250_0
$-0.63 \pm 13.34^\circ$ <div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">+0.69%</div>	$39.43 \pm 27.67^\circ$ <div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">-6.14%</div>	$89.75 \pm 1.93^\circ$ <div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">-0.28%</div>	$3.66 \pm 13.02^\circ$ <div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">+4.03%</div>

Conclusions

- FFF is a highly versatile fabrication technique, capable of inducing anisotropy.
 - Mechanical properties of FFF fabricated materials somewhat resemble those of micro-composites – even in pure materials.
- FFF of nanocomposites affects the dispersion and alignment of the nanoparticles within the matrix – allowing another degree of control in the design.
- The effect of FFF on the nanoparticles in the nanocomposite depends on the morphology of the nanoparticles.

And we haven't discussed hybrids yet

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